

Abstract

To date there are some studies addressing the effects of the menstrual cycle on the biomechanics and neuromuscular control during athletic movements. Even though some studies did measure actual hormonal levels, the analyses were primarily done based on the phase of the menstrual cycle. But it is not the phase of the menstrual cycle that acts on the bodily structures, it is effective hormonal levels that are relevant and need to be studied. Despite ongoing research, there is contradictory information on when ligamentous injuries occur in relation to the menstrual cycle. There is a lack of knowledge on how hormones influence biomechanical properties and the variables related to ligamentous. To understand the effect of hormones on biomechanics, it is necessary to consider hormonal levels and assess the combined effect of multiple hormones affecting the musculoskeletal system.

This protocol describes the detailed procedures for the collection of data for a study that aims to identify the influence of the hormonal profile on biomechanical variables during functional assessments related to ligamentous lower extremity injuries in female recreational athletes.

Study Design

The study is designed as an observational study with multiple observation time points. After a screening visit and a tracking phase of two menstrual cycles, four observations per menstrual cycle over two menstrual cycles will be collected at the ZHAW (Zurich University of Applied Sciences) in Winterthur.

The primary outcome measure will be the biomechanical variables related to acute ligamentous lower extremity injuries. The explanatory variables will be sex hormone levels and training volume (fixed effects). Each interaction for timepoint and participant will be random effects.

The following variables are related to acute ligamentous lower extremity injuries and serve as the primary outcome variables of this study:

- Peak hip flexion angles
- Peak knee, flexion, abduction, and internal rotation angles
- Peak knee flexion and abduction moments
- Peak ankle plantarflexion, dorsiflexion, and inversion angles
- Ankle dorsiflexion/plantarflexion and eversion/inversion range of motion
- Peak ankle inversion velocity
- Peak ankle plantarflexion and internal rotation moments
- Muscle activity of: M. gastrocnemius medialis and lateralis, M. peroneus longus, M. semitendinosus, M. biceps femoris, M. gluteus medius, M. vastus medialis and lateralis
- Static and dynamic postural balance

The hormonal profile may influence the primary outcome measures, and this relationship is under investigation. The hormonal profile is defined through the concentrations of estrogen, progesterone, luteinizing hormone (LH), and follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) in the blood serum.

Muscle strength of the lower extremities, core endurance as well as passive range of motion may influence the measures of these variables and will therefore be measured once during the screening visit.

Information and expression of interest

Interested potential participants can fill out an online questionnaire via REDCap (Vanderbilt University, 2004) to express their interest in the study. This questionnaire queries the basic inclusion and exclusion criteria. After submission study personnel will contact the potential participants by phone to provide detailed information about the study procedures, verify the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and schedule the screening visit.

A reminder E-Mail, including the informed consent form is sent to the participants 24 hours prior to the screening visit to ensure they are given enough time for informed decision making.

Screening visit

Informed consent form

Upon arrival, the informed consent form is reviewed and explained once again. After signing informed written consent, detailed screening questions will be asked to assess the inclusion and exclusion criteria, obtain patient reported medical history and further details about their menstrual cycle.

Inclusion criteria

- female sex
- recreational athletes with 3-10 hours of exercise per week
- 18-34 years of age
- eumenorrheic: self-reported cycle length between 24 and 35 days resulting in at least 9 periods per year or users of non-hormonal (copper) intrauterine contraceptive devices
- no injuries requiring medical attention or rehabilitation during the last 6 months
- able to perform jumping, hopping, and cutting movements
- Body mass index < 28 kg/m²
- willingness to apply the TAP®-Device for minimally invasive blood analysis
- ability to give informed consent

Exclusion criteria

- complete rupture of ligaments in the lower extremities
- surgical reconstruction of ligaments in the lower extremities
- pregnancy or breast feeding
- acute or chronic diseases (neurological, cardiopulmonary, musculoskeletal, untreated endocrinologic disorder)
- use of systemic effective hormonal contraceptives
- any kind of hormone replacement therapy in the past 3 months
- any kind of anti-hormonal therapy

Participant preparation

After inclusion, the participant is asked to change into shorts, sports bra and indoor sports shoes, provided by the study site.

Palpation and marking of anatomical landmarks

The following anatomical landmarks are marked:

- anterior superior iliac spine
- epicondylus lateralis femoris
- head of fibula

- malleolus lateralis
- malleolus medialis
- sternum

Collection of anthropometric data

Height (in cm), body mass (in kg) and leg length are measured without shoes. Leg length is defined as the distance between anterior superior iliac spine to the patella and then to the medial malleolus (in cm). To measure the height, the participant is instructed to stand upright with the heels touching the wall and the back against a measuring tape fixed to the wall. The measuring stick is positioned at the apex of the head to record the height. Body mass is measured using a conventional scale.

Warm-up

A standardized warm-up is instructed and will be part of all nine measurements.

	Exercise	Reps/Time/Distance	Details
Pillar prep with stretching	Deep Squat and Hamstring Stretch	8x	
	Glute Bridge Walk Out	3x	
	Walkout with Shoulder Taps	3x	Stand up in between
	World Greatest stretch	3x es (each side)	Stand up in between
General Warmup	Jog line to line	4x20m	
	Backward (bw) / sideward (sw) running	4x20m (bw, sw, bw, sw)	
Strengthening	Walking Lunges with rotation	1x5 es	
	Single toe raises with hip flexion	1x10	
Plyometrics	Squat jumps	1x5	Continuous
	Skater jumps	1x5 (es)	Increasing width
	Single leg hops lateral	6''	Over line, without break
	Single leg hops forward / backward	6''	Over line, without break
Agilities	Forward run with 3 step decelerations	3x	Stop before red line
	Figure 8	2x	Around the black edges of force plates

Table 1 Warmup based on a modified version of the Prevent injury and Enhance Performance Program according to Mandelbaum et al. (2005).

Passive range of motion

The passive range of motion of the ankle, knee, and hip joints is assessed using the EasyAngle goniometer (Meloq, Stockholm, Sweden). Participants are positioned on a massage table to ensure standardization of measurement. The measurement protocol for each joint is described below.

Ankle Joint

Dorsiflexion:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: The investigator holds the participant's heel, presses their forearm against the sole and moves the ankle into maximal dorsiflexion (Figure 1).
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed vertically relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the lateral edge of the foot.

Figure 1. Passive range of motion of ankle dorsiflexion.

Plantarflexion:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: The investigator applies pressure on the forefoot to achieve maximal plantarflexion (Figure 2).
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed vertically relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the lateral edge of the foot.

Figure 2. Passive range of motion of ankle plantarflexion.

Inversion:

- Position: The participant lies in prone position with feet extending beyond the edge of the massage table.
- Procedure: The investigator pushes the ankle into maximal inversion (Figure 3) while stabilizing the lower shank.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed parallel to the horizontal plane of the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the heel to the Achilles tendon.

Figure 3. Passive range of motion of ankle inversion.

Eversion:

- Position: The participant lies in prone position with feet extending beyond the massage table edge.
- Procedure: The investigator pushes the ankle into maximal eversion (Figure 4) while stabilizing the lower shank.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed parallel to the horizontal plane of the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the heel to the Achilles tendon.

Figure 4. Passive range of motion of ankle eversion.

Knee Joint

Flexion:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: The participant actively pulls the heel toward the hip. The investigator applies additional pressure on the shank to achieve maximal flexion (Figure 5).
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed along the line from the greater trochanter to the lateral femoral epicondyle, and the angle is measured along the line from the fibular head to the lateral malleolus.

Figure 5. Passive range of motion of knee flexion.

Extension:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: A second investigator stabilizes the upper thigh and pulls the shank into maximal knee extension (Figure 6), while the primary investigator measures the angle.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the fibular head to the lateral malleolus.

Figure 6. Passive range of motion of knee extension.

Hip Joint

Internal Rotation:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: The investigator flexes the hip and knee to 90° each and rotates the lower leg laterally (Figure 7) while stabilizing the upper thigh.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the tibial axis.

Figure 7. Passive range of motion of hip internal rotation.

External Rotation:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: The investigator flexes the hip and knee to 90° each and rotates the lower leg medially (Figure 8) while stabilizing the upper thigh.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the tibial axis.

Figure 8. Passive range of motion of hip external rotation.

Abduction:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: A second investigator stabilizes the pelvis, while the primary investigator abducts the leg (Figure 9) until pelvic motion is detected.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS) to the patella.

Figure 9. Passive range of motion of hip abduction.

Adduction:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position. The contralateral hip is flexed and held by the participant.
- Procedure: A second investigator stabilizes the pelvis, while the primary investigator adducts the extended leg (Figure 10) until pelvic motion is detected.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the ASIS to the patella.

Figure 10. Passive range of motion of hip adduction.

Flexion:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position with knees extended.
- Procedure: The investigator flexes the hip and knee, applying pressure on the shank to achieve maximal hip flexion (Figure 11).
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the greater trochanter to the lateral femoral epicondyle.

Figure 11. Passive range of motion of hip flexion.

Extension:

- Position: The participant lies in prone position with knees extended.
- Procedure: A second investigator stabilizes the pelvis, while the investigator extends the hip (Figure 12) until pelvic motion is detected.
- Measurement: The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the massage table, and the angle is measured along the line from the greater trochanter to the lateral femoral epicondyle.

Figure 12. Passive range of motion of hip flexion.

Strength test

The strength of the lower extremities is assessed using the EasyForce pull dynamometer (Meloq, Stockholm, Sweden). Participants are instructed to pull gradually and increase force over a duration of 5 seconds. Each side is tested with one familiarization trial followed by two measured trials. The dynamometer is attached to a wall-mounted strap, which can be secured around the relevant body part. The joint angle at which the force is measured is standardized using the EasyAngle goniometer.

Hip Joint

Abduction:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position on a yoga mat with the upper body stabilized against a box positioned against the wall. The hip and knee closer to the wall are flexed, the testing leg is extended with the band secured around the ankle.
- Procedure: The participant abducts the hip against the resistance of the strap (Figure 13) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° hip abduction. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally parallel to the wall, and the angle is measured on the thigh (ASIS to patella).

Figure 13. Strength test of hip abduction.

Adduction:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position on a yoga mat with the upper body stabilized against a box. Both legs are extended, and the band is attached to the ankle of the leg closer to the wall.
- Procedure: The participant adducts the hip against the resistance of the strap (Figure 14) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° hip adduction. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally parallel to the wall, and the angle is measured on the thigh (ASIS to patella).

Figure 14. Strength test of hip adduction.

Flexion:

- Position: The participant lies in supine position on a yoga mat with legs extended and feet touching the wall. The testing leg is flexed to a 90° hip angle and 90° knee angle, with the band secured around the thigh.
- Procedure: The participant flexes the hip against the resistance of the strap (Figure 15) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 90° hip flexion. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally relative to the floor, and the angle is measured on the thigh (greater trochanter to lateral femoral epicondyle).

Figure 15. Strength test of hip flexion.

Extension:

- Position: The participant lies in prone position on a massage table, with legs extended and feet hanging off the edge of the massage table. The massage table is positioned 20 cm away from the wall. The band is attached around the ankle of the testing leg.
- Procedure: The participant extends the hip against the resistance of the strap (Figure 16) away from the table.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° hip extension. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the massage table, and the angle is measured on the shank (fibular head to lateral malleolus).

Figure 16. Strength test of hip extension.

Internal Rotation:

- Position: The participant sits on a massage table with hands resting on the thighs. The massage table is positioned perpendicular to the wall. The band is attached to the ankle of the testing leg (further from the wall), and the other leg rests on the frame of the massage table.
- Procedure: The participant performs internal rotation of the hip against the resistance of the strap (Figure 17) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° hip internal rotation. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the massage table, and the angle (90°) is measured on the tibia.

Figure 17. Strength test of hip internal rotation.

External Rotation:

- Position: The participant sits on a massage table with hands resting on the thighs. The massage table is positioned perpendicular to the wall. The band is attached to the ankle of the testing leg (closer to the wall).
- Procedure: The participant performs external rotation of the hip against the resistance of the strap (Figure 18) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° hip external rotation. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the massage table, and the angle (90°) is measured on the tibia.

Figure 18. Strength test of hip external rotation.

Knee Joint

Flexion:

- Position: The participant lies in prone position on a yoga mat with legs extended and feet touching the wall. The testing leg is flexed to a 90° knee angle, and the band is secured around the ankle.
- Procedure: The participant flexes the knee against the resistance of the strap (Figure 19) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 90° knee flexion. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the floor, and the angle is measured on the shank (fibular head to lateral malleolus).

Figure 19. Strength test of knee flexion.

Extension:

- Position: The participant sits on a massage table with hands resting on the thighs. The massage table is positioned parallel to the wall, and the band is secured around the ankle of the testing leg.
- Procedure: The participant extends the knee against the resistance of the strap (Figure 20) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 90° knee flexion. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the massage table, and the angle is measured on the shank (fibular head to lateral malleolus).

Figure 20. Strength test of knee extension.

Ankle Joint

Dorsiflexion:

- Position: The participant sits on a yoga mat facing the wall with legs extended. The band is secured around the forefoot of the testing leg in a neutral ankle position. Arms are placed behind the body for support.
- Procedure: The participant performs dorsiflexion against the resistance of the strap (Figure 21) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° dorsiflexion. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the floor, and the angle (90°) is measured on the lateral edge of the shoe.

Figure 21. Strength test of ankle dorsiflexion.

Plantarflexion:

- Position: The participant sits on a yoga mat with the back supported by the wall and legs extended. The band is secured around the forefoot of the testing leg.
- Procedure: The participant performs plantarflexion against the resistance of the strap (Figure 22) away from the wall.
- Measurement: The force is measured at 0° plantarflexion. The goniometer is zeroed horizontally on the floor, and the angle (90°) is measured on the lateral edge of the shoe.

Figure 22. Strength test of ankle plantarflexion.

Core endurance test

Core endurance is assessed according to the Swiss Olympics test protocol (Leistungsdiagnostik Manual p. 58 ff). The tests are performed dynamically and continued as long as the participant can maintain proper form. The procedures for each test are as follows:

Prone Bridge Test

- Position: The participant assumes a front plank position with the head touching a box. The upper arms are vertical, the forearms are parallel and shoulder-width apart, with thumbs pointing upward. The posterior superior iliac spine (PSIS) touches a crossbar set at the height where the shoulder joint center, greater trochanter, and lateral malleolus form a straight line.
- Procedure: The participant lifts their feet alternately with straight knees at one-second intervals guided by a metronome (Figure 23). Timing begins when the pelvis touches the crossbar.
- Termination Criteria (two warnings):
 - Loss of consistent contact between the pelvis and the crossbar.
 - Inability to maintain the one-second rhythm.

Figure 23. Prone Bridge Test.

Side Bridge Test

- Position: The participant assumes a side plank position with the back against a wall. The feet are stacked, with the heels, shoulder blades, and hips in contact with the wall. The upper arm on the supporting side is vertical, and the free hand rests on the iliac crest. The greater trochanter touches a crossbar set at the height where the medial malleolus, symphysis pubis, navel, and jugular notch form a straight line.
- Procedure: The participant lifts and lowers the pelvis at one-second intervals guided by a metronome (Figure 24). Timing begins when the pelvis first touches the crossbar.
- Termination Criteria (two warnings):
 - Incomplete movement cycles.
 - Supporting oneself on the floor.
 - Loss of wall contact.

Figure 24. Side Bridge Test.

Sorensen Test

- Position: The participant lies prone on a massage table, with the anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS) positioned 5 cm behind the massage table's front edge. The feet are secured under padded supports, with the heels firmly in contact. A lower crossbar is set at 30° trunk flexion (contact at the sternum), and an upper crossbar is set at 0° trunk flexion (contact at the upper back). The arms are crossed, with the fingers resting on the clavicles, and the elbows remain in front of the lower crossbar.
- Procedure: The participant lifts and lowers the upper body, lightly touching both crossbars at one-second intervals guided by a metronome (Figure 25). Timing begins when the upper crossbar is touched for the first time.
- Termination Criteria (two warnings):
 - Incomplete movement cycles.
 - Leaning on the lower crossbar.

Figure 25. Sorensen Test.

Rest and Instruction Period

A 10-minute break is mandatory between each core endurance test. During these breaks, participants are instructed on the following:

- Usage of the TAP® device.
- Instructions for the tracking phase.
- Instruction of functional assessments for upcoming visits.

TAP®-Device

For the measurement of the hormone concentrations, the participant is asked to draw blood in the morning of each functional assessment as well as during the screening visit. The blood draw is performed using a TAP®-Device (YourBio Health Inc., Medford, MA, USA), which allows for a minimally invasive, pain free, and standardized capillary blood draw (Figure 26). It is based on microneedle technology and can be performed by the participants themselves. During the screening visit, the investigator provides detailed instructions on the handling of the TAP®-Device and the blood sample in accordance with the manufacturer's guidelines.

Figure 26. TAP®-Device.

Timepoints of hormone measurement

The steroid hormones, LH and prolactin are collected every morning of the eight functional assessments. Participants are instructed to securely package the collected samples and bring them to the laboratory. Study staff then facilitates the transfer of these samples to the SwissAnalysis AG laboratory (Tägerwil, Switzerland) for analysis. FSH, Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) and thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) are only collected once during the screening visit using an additional TAP®-Device. AMH and TSH are not expected to fluctuate during the menstrual cycle. FSH is only measured once due to the limited volume of the TAP®-Device, and its close correlation with LH.

Instruction of tracking phase

In order to track the menstrual cycle after the screening visit, a link to the REDCap tracking instrument is sent to the participant. To determine the timing of ovulation, the participant is provided with 15 ovulation tests from Pinkline (Pinkline by Burggraf, Taverne, Switzerland). The participant is instructed to perform the first ovulation test two days before the predicted ovulation based on the self-reported cycle length. The test is repeated until a positive test results. The ovulation test are used according to the manufacturer's guideline. The tracking phase begins with the first onset of bleeding after the screening visit. The participant records the onset of bleeding and positive ovulation tests during the next two menstrual cycles and submits the results using the REDCap tracking instrument.

Instruction of functional assessments

All functional assessments are instructed by the study personnel and exercised by the participant. This approach ensures that participants clearly understand the expectations and are familiarized with the procedures for subsequent visits.

Schedules for functional assessments

After the participant reports two positive ovulation tests, a gynecologist who is part of the study team determines the timepoints for the first four measurements of the functional assessments. The measurements take place during four specific phases of the menstrual cycle. The process is repeated for a second menstrual cycle. The phases are defined as follows:

- Phase 1 starts on the second day of bleeding and lasts four days. The intention is to capture the lowest estrogen, progesterone, and LH concentrations during the early follicular phase.
- Phase 2 is during the late follicular, pre-ovulatory phase. The intention is to capture the ascending and highest estrogen concentration while progesterone remains low. LH and FSH begin to increase immediately prior to ovulation.
- Phase 3 is during the ovulatory phase, optimally 24 hours after ovulation. The intention is to capture medium estrogen and, low progesterone concentration, while LH and FSH are still high.
- Phase 4 is during the luteal phase, starting five to seven days after confirmed ovulation. The intention is to capture the highest progesterone concentration (> 8 ng/ml) and intermediate estrogen concentration (> 100 pg/ml) while LH and FSH concentrations are low.

The participant is asked to continue the tracking of the onset of bleeding and ovulation to make sure the schedule for the functional assessments is correct. If the onset of bleeding or the ovulation are earlier or later than predicted, the gynecologist is contacted again, and the timepoints are adjusted. After the positive ovulation test between the measurements of phases 2 and 3 the gynecologist determines the timepoints for the measurements of the second menstrual cycle.

Laboratory preparation

Biomechanical data is collected using three-dimensional motion capture (Vicon, Oxford, UK), force plates (Advanced Mechanical Technology Incorporation, Watertown, USA), and surface electromyography (EMG, Cometa srl, Baleggio, Italy). A total of 11 Vicon Vantage cameras, two DV cameras, 16 EMG sensors and two force plates are used for data collection. To ensure proper functioning, the Vicon Vantage Cameras need to be warmed up and therefore be turned on at least 60 minutes prior to system calibration.

The camera system must be calibrated according to the manufacturer's guidelines. The calibration procedure for the Vicon system can be referenced in the official guidelines provided here:

[Calibrate a Vicon system - Nexus 2.16 documentation - Vicon Help](#)

Participant preparation

The participant is given the same clothing and shoes as worn during the screening visit.

Collection of anthropometric data

Height (in cm) and body mass (in kg) are measured without shoes. To measure the height, the participant is asked to stand upright with the heels touching the wall and the back leaning against a measuring tape stuck to the wall. The measuring stick is guided to the apex where the height is measured. The mass is measured with a conventional scale.

Palpation and marking of anatomical landmarks

The following anatomical landmarks are marked bilaterally (where applicable):

while standing

- anterior superior iliac spine
- posterior superior iliac spine
- joint space in front of the anterior border of the medial knee ligament
- lateral side of patella
- epicondylus medialis femoris
- epicondylus lateralis femoris
- epicondylus medialis tibialis
- epicondylus lateralis tibialis
- head of fibula
- malleolus lateralis
- malleolus medialis
- C7
- clavícula
- sternum

while laying on either side

- trochanter major
- crista iliaca

Warm-up

The same warm-up as in the screening visit is performed.

EMG placement

EMG sensors will be placed on the muscles of both legs following the SENIAM recommendations ([Sensor Locations](#)). The EMG sensors will be secured using elastotape. All sensors will be placed while the participant is lying down, except for the sensors of the M. gastrocnemius lateralis and medialis, which will be placed in a standing position. The sensors will be placed in the following order:

- M. gluteus medius
- M. vastus medialis
- M. vastus lateralis
- M. peroneus longus
- M. gastrocnemius medialis
- M. gastrocnemius lateralis
- M. biceps femoris
- M. semitendinosus

Maximum Voluntary Contraction (MVC) Testing Protocol

MVC measurements are conducted for all recorded muscles. The participant is instructed to gradually increase force to maximum effort over 3–5 seconds, maintain maximum effort for 3 seconds, and then gradually release the force over the next 3 seconds. Each muscle is tested twice. Joint angles during force measurement are controlled using the EasyAngle device. The order of measurement is as follows and the starting side is randomised:

M. Gluteus Medius

- Position: The participant lies on their side on a massage table with the lower leg slightly flexed and the upper leg extended, resting on two blocks. A belt secures the upper leg to the massage table to prevent lifting. The upper body remains relaxed.
- Procedure: The participant is instructed to attempt to lift the upper leg against the resistance of the belt (Figure 27). The MVC is measured at 0° hip abduction.
- Reference Points: Zero is set horizontally on the massage table. The angle is measured on the thigh using the line from the patella to the anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS).

Figure 27. MVC of the M. Gluteus Medius.

M. Vastus Medialis and M. Vastus Lateralis

- Position: The participant sits on a massage table, hands resting on their thighs. The massage table is oriented horizontally along the wall. A strap is secured to the wall and around the participant's ankle.
- Procedure: The participant is instructed to attempt knee extension against the resistance of the strap (Figure 28) away from the wall. The MVC is measured at 90° knee flexion.
- Reference Points: Zero is set horizontally on the massage table. The angle (90°) is measured on the shank using the line from the fibular head to the lateral malleolus.

Figure 28. MVC of the Mm. Vasti Medialis and Lateralis.

M. Peroneus Longus

- Position: The participant sits on the floor with legs extended, facing the wall. A strap is attached to the wall and around the forefoot.
- Procedure: The participant is instructed to attempt to pull the outer edge of the foot against the resistance of the strap (Figure 29) away from the wall. The MVC is measured at 0° dorsal extension.
- Reference Points: Zero is set horizontally on the floor. The angle (90°) is measured on the outer edge of the shoe.

Figure 29. MVC of the M. Peroneus Longus.

M. Gastrocnemius Medialis and M. Gastrocnemius Lateralis

- Positioning: The participant sits on the floor, back resting against the wall. Legs are extended, and the testing leg is slightly elevated with the foot placed on a board. A strap is attached to the wall and around the forefoot, maintaining a neutral ankle position.
- Procedure: The participant is instructed to attempt to push the forefoot against the resistance of the strap (Figure 30) away from the wall. The MVC is measured at 0° plantarflexion.
- Reference Points: Zero is set on the shank using the line from fibular head to the lateral malleolus. The angle (90°) is measured on the outer edge of the shoe.

Figure 30. MVC of the Mm. Gastrocnemii Medialis and Lateralis.

M. Biceps Femoris and M. Semitendinosus

- Positioning: The participant lies in prone position on a yoga mat, with legs extended. A strap is secured to the wall and around the ankle of the flexed leg.
- Procedure: The participant is instructed to attempt to pull the heel against the resistance of the strap (Figure 31) away from the wall. The MVC is measured at 30° knee flexion.
- Reference Points: Zero is set horizontally on the floor. The angle is measured on the shank using the line from the fibular head to the lateral malleolus.

Figure 31. MVC of the M. Biceps Femoris and M. Semitendinosus.

Participant preparation

Marker placement

A cluster marker model is used for kinematic and kinetic analysis (Figure 32). Prior to attaching the markers (16mm), a tape spray is applied to enhance skin adhesion.

Table 1: Marker names and placement

Segment	Marker name	Position
Foot	L/R HeePoDis	Left / Right Heel Posterior Distal (centred on posterior aspect of the heel, just above the shoe sole)
	L/R HeePoPro	Left / Right Heel Posterior Proximal (above HeePoDis, centred on posterior aspect of the heel)
	L/R HeeLaTer	Left / Right Lateral Heel
	L/R HeeMeDia	Left / Right lateral of HeeLaTer
Shank	L/R AnkMeMal	Left / Right ankle medial malleolus (on the most prominent part)
	L/R AnkLaMal	Left / Right ankle lateral malleolus (on the most prominent part)
	L/R ShaLoLat	Left / Right shank lower lateral
	L/R ShaLoMed	Left / Right shank lower medial (preferably on the shin)
	L/R ShaUpLat	Left / Right shank upper lateral
	L/R ShaUpMed	Left / Right shank upper medial (preferably on the shin)
Thigh	L/R KneLaEpi	Left / Right knee lateral epicondyle
	L/R KneMeEpi	Left / Right knee medial epicondyle
	L/R ThiLoMed	Left / Right thigh lower medial (above the patella)
	L/R ThiLoLat	Left / Right thigh lower lateral
	L/R ThiUpMed	Left / Right thigh upper medial
Pelvis	L/R ThiUpLat	Left / Right thigh upper lateral (below the fingers, when arms are hold beside the body)
	L/R ASI	Placed directly over the left / right anterior superior iliac spine
	L/R PSI	Placed directly over the left / right posterior superior iliac spine
Trunk	CLAV	on the jugular notch where the clavicles meet the sternum
	STRN	on the sternum below CLAV
	C7	on the spinous process of the 7 th cervical vertebra

The markers on the knee and ankle are removed after the static trial and the functional calibration.

Figure 32. Marker placement on subject's body.

Data collection

Static trial

For the static trial, the participant is asked to stand hip-width apart on a wooden plate, with their heels touching the back edge of the plate (Figure 33). The individual stance width is measured using additional wooden plates to ensure consistent stance width is maintained across all eight measurements. The following verbal instruction will be provided:

"Stand still and upright, place your hands on either side of the upper body above the waist".

After the static trial, the markers are labeled in the Nexus software, to confirm that all markers are present and properly recognised by the cameras.

Figure 33. Alignment device to ensure consistent stance width across eight measurements.

Functional calibration

The functional calibration of the hip and knee joint will be performed according to List et al. (2013). The following verbal instruction will be given:

Knee

"Stand upright. Lift your left/right leg off the floor and move your lower leg up to your thigh and back again three times."

Hip

"Stand upright. Lift your left/right leg off the floor and circle your outstretched leg around your hip three times. The circle should be as large as possible."

Clinical parameters

Single-Leg Balance Test

- Setup: The participant stands on one leg in the center of a force plate. Hands are placed on either side of the upper body above the waist. The participant focuses on a cross positioned at 1.66 m height on the wall in front of them.
- Procedure: Once the participant feels balanced, they close their eyes and attempt to maintain balance for 10 seconds. The participant is instructed to avoid moving the standing foot, releasing their hands from either side of the upper body above the waist, or allowing the legs to touch each other.
- Repetitions and Trials: The test is conducted twice on each leg. A single practice trial is permitted for each leg.

Modified Star Excursion Balance Test (mSEBT)

- Setup: A "Y" shape is created on the floor using black adhesive tape. The angles between the anterior tape and the posterolateral and posteromedial are 135°. The angle between the posterolateral and posteromedial tape is 90°. A marker is attached to the shoe at the tip of the big toe to facilitate measurement in all directions using the Nexus software. The standing leg is placed at the intersection of the "Y," ensuring the shoe marker aligns with the center of the intersect.
- Procedure: The participant stands on the testing leg, with hands on either side of the upper body above the waist, maintaining an upright posture. They are instructed to reach as far as possible with the non-standing leg and to lightly tap the floor in the anterior, posterolateral, and posteromedial direction. The participant must avoid losing balance, releasing the hands from either side of the upper body above the waist, or shifting the standing leg.
- Repetitions and Trials: The test is performed twice for each leg. A single practice trial is allowed for each leg.

Functional assessments

Five different functional assessments are captured during each of the eight time points. The order of the functional assessment is randomized for each time point. Each assessment is performed five times, with an additional repetition allowed in case of a fault. Participants are allowed one practice trial per assessment.

Drop Vertical Jump - Bilateral

- Setup: A 30 cm high box is positioned 10 cm behind the force plate.
- Procedure: The participant stands on the box with hands placed on either side of the upper body above the waist. The participant is instructed to drop off the box, land with both feet on the force plates (one foot per plate), have a minimal ground contact time, and jump as high as possible.

Drop Vertical Jump - Unilateral

- Setup: A 30 cm high box is positioned 10 cm behind the force plates.
- Procedure: The participant stands on the box with hands on either side of the upper body above the waist. The participant is instructed to drop off the box, land with one foot on the

corresponding force plate, have a minimal ground contact time, and jump as high as possible. The second landing is performed with both legs.

- Trials are alternated between legs.

Side Hop Test

- Setup: Two parallel lines are marked 30 cm apart on the force plates.
- Procedure: The participant stands with hands on either side of the upper body above the waist and the tested leg is positioned with the inside edge of the foot laterally to the line. The participant performs 10 consecutive single-leg hops across the two lines.
- Key Criteria:
 - The jumping foot must not touch the lines
 - The jumping foot must always land entirely on the force plates.
 - The non-jumping foot must not touch the ground.
 - The hands must remain on either side of the upper body above the waist throughout the test.
 - The final landing must be stabilized and held momentarily.
- Trials are alternated between legs.

Cutting Maneuver

- Setup: Photocells are placed 1.92 m before and after the midpoint of the two force plates. The photocells after the force plate are angled at 45° from the center of the second force plate.
- Procedure: The participant accelerates for 6 m, performs a cutting maneuver on the second force plate, and sprints through the second set of photocells. The participant is instructed to maintain a forward gaze without looking down.
- Key Criteria:
 - The velocity between the photocells must exceed 3.5 m/s.
 - Trials must remain within $\pm 10\%$ of the average speed recorded at the first time point.
- All trials are performed for one side before switching to the other.

Pivot Maneuver

- Setup: Photocells are placed 5 m before the midpoint of the second force plate.
- Procedure: The participant accelerates for 6 m, performs a 180° turn on the second force plate, and sprints back through the same photocells. The participant is instructed to maintain a forward gaze without looking down.
- Key Criteria:
 - The velocity during the maneuver must exceed 3.2 m/s.
 - Trials must remain within $\pm 10\%$ of the average speed recorded at the first time point.
- All trials are performed for one side before switching to the other.

End of data collection

After all data has been collected, the markers and the EMG sensors are removed from the participant who is then free to change and leave.

Data backup

The collected data is backed up to the secure laboratory network access drive.